

Analysis of Green Product and Green Advertising on Purchase Decision of Aqua Products Mediated by Green Trust

Fahmi Muhammad Kusumah, Dudi Permana
Universitas Mercu Buana, Jakarta,
Indonesia

Abstract:- Environmental pollution can occur due to the lack of public knowledge about the environment. Under these conditions, companies are competing to innovate to create green products. Currently green products in Indonesia are widely circulated among consumers, with the concept of Green Products it is necessary to promote continuously and consistently so that consumers know green products in more depth through advertising. The purpose of this study is to determine the factors that can influence the purchase decision of Aqua products. Hypothesis testing in this study will be carried out using the Partial Least Square (PLS) based Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach. Based on the research results, green product and green advertising have a significant effect on green trust, while green trust has a significant effect on decisions, but green product and green advertising have no significant effect on purchasing decisions. Green trust mediates the pseudo-relationship between green products and purchasing decisions, Green trust also mediates the pseudo-relationship between green advertising and purchasing decisions.

Keywords:- Green Product, Green Advertising, Green Trust, Purchase Decision, Aqua.

I. INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution can occur due to the lack of public knowledge about the environment and how to manage the environment. Environmental pollution can be caused by the problem of garbage, industrial waste, and human behavior itself. Therefore companies are competing to innovate in creating green products. Baqirah (2019) said that the amount of landfill waste in Indonesia is 175,000 tons per day or 64 tons per year and plastic waste contributes 15%. This makes people aware that the products consumed can have a damaging impact on the environment if not managed properly. Some consumers have started to be aware and selective in purchasing environmentally friendly products. According to Arifia (2019), this phenomenon occurs because awareness begins in the minds of consumers on environmental issues. Based on Oktaviani (2017), the determining factor in purchasing green products is the cleanliness of the product to the impact on health.

Changes in consumer behavior are exploited by companies that compete to be able to reach consumers. Therefore the company created a marketing concept, namely selling products that use environmentally friendly materials

on their packaging. Manongko (2018) said that changes in consumer behavior that use environmentally friendly products is a reflection of public concern for maintaining and protecting the environment. To deal with the problem of environmental damage, not only the community but the government must also take part by increasing awareness and concern for environmental damage (Rasaputra and Sam, 2015). One of the efforts is by creating, introducing, and using green products. Green product is a product whose design, production or strategy uses recycled, renewable, non-toxic resources and can reduce the impact of environmental damage (Durif, 2012). The concept of Green Products in Indonesia needs to be promoted on an ongoing basis so that consumers can know more about green products.

Green advertising is green advertising that aims to promote products and services that contain the company's commitment to reduce environmental damage so that it can provide an image of a company that cares about the environment (Santoso and Rengganis, 2016). Green product advertisements can be made more attractive, different and unique compared to other products (Ardiansyah, Zainul and Dahlan, 2015), must be informative and contain the company's concrete actions in the environmental preservation movement and also provide a more natural product description (Richards, 2013). In Indonesia itself, currently there are many green advertisements. An example of such a green ad is the Aqua ad which campaigns for one bottle of aqua to be exchanged for one tree which can be monitored in real-time.

With environmentally friendly advertising, it is hoped that it can meet the needs and desires of consumers and the environment, and can also foster consumer confidence. Trust is a person's belief in other parties that they can be relied upon because they are committed to their promises and can create a sense of security (Ling, Dazmin, Tan, Kay and Padzil, 2011). Trust can encourage consumers to make purchasing decisions. (Astini, 2016). Green trust is strongly influenced by consumer confidence in the safety of environmentally friendly products (Santoso and Rengganis, 2016). With environmental decisions and considerations, consumers will prefer environmentally friendly products over others. Other considerations in buying a product are because it is affordable (Albari and Indah, 2017), social influence (Anvar and Marike, 2014) and ease of obtaining products (Brata, Shilvana and Hapzi, 2017).

In Indonesia, one example of a company that provides environmentally friendly products is PT. Danone Indonesia, which produces mineral water under the Aqua brand (aqua.co.id, 2020), is in accordance with the company's vision, namely one planet, one health, which means that

Aqua believes that a healthy lifestyle and a healthy environment will provide health to the community. Aqua products have always been at the top of the top mineral water brands in Indonesia, along with the top mineral water brands from 2017 - 2021:

Top Brand Air Mineral									
2017		2018		2019		2020		2021	
Merk	TBI	Merk	TBI	Merk	TBI	Merk	TBI	Merk	TBI
Aqua	73.3%	Aqua	63.9%	Aqua	61%	Aqua	61.5%	Aqua	62.5%
Vit	6.1%	Ades	7.6%	Ades	6%	Ades	7.8%	Ades	7.5%
Club	4.5%	Club	3.4%	Club	5.1%	Club	6.6%	Club	5.8%
Ades	4.1%	2Tang	3.2%	Le Minerale	5%	Le Minerale	6.1%	Le Minerale	4.6%

Table 1: Top Brand Air Mineral 2017-2021

Source: www.topbrand-award.com

Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency for 2021 which states that plastic waste in Indonesia has reached 66 million tonnes per year. From the table it can be seen that Aqua is very influential on plastic waste in Indonesia, this is because Aqua is the top brand of bottled drinking water so that there are many Aqua packages circulating in Indonesia. So Aqua needs to carry out an environmental care movement in order to reduce the growth of plastic waste. Research conducted by Maria (2019) said that the contents and packaging of green products will affect the level of consumer confidence in environmentally friendly drinks, the greater the influence of advertising will also increase consumer confidence in environmentally friendly drinks, and the presence of green products will reduce the impact of environmental damage.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

With increasing competition and expectations from all companies, a company must have three pillars, namely Adaptability, Systemic Resilience, and Sustainability. The company's success is not only the company's ability to meet consumer needs, but the company must also be able to maintain the environment in which the company operates. The company is the center of environmental destruction, but the company is also the key to cleaner and environmentally friendly business practices. So it is necessary to have the pillar concept of the Triple Bottom Line, which is a framework to help companies move towards a sustainable future. Companies that implement the Triple Bottom Line concept, means that the company is committed to measuring

financial performance as well as social and environmental impacts.

Products are goods or services produced through processes (Hamid, 2017). According to Albino, Balice and Dangelico (2009), a product can be called green if the product has good functions and performance for the environment. Green product is a product that has a design, attribute, production or strategy using recycled, renewable, non-toxic resources, and can reduce the impact of environmental damage (Durif et al, 2010). Based on Kotler and Armstrong (2016: 177) purchase decision is part of a consumer behavior, which is learning about how an individual, a group, or an organization can choose, buy, use and how an item, service, idea or experience can be sufficient their needs and wants. According to Khuong and Hoang (2016), purchase decisions include 3 activities by consumers, namely buying, consuming, and disposing of products. Companies continue to make their products unique so they can be different from competing products and can also attract consumers by promoting environmentally friendly products through advertising (D'Souza and Taghian, 2005). According to Liliweri (2011), advertising is any activity that promotes ideas, goods or services. The purpose of advertising is to provide information, persuade and remind. Green advertising is green advertising in which it promotes green products that aim to attract consumers who care about the environment (Ridwan et al, 2018). According to Kurniawan (2014), green trust is trust that comes from the ability of environmental performance to depend on a product. Based on the description above, the research framework is compiled:

Picture 1: Research Framework

The hypothesis that is structured based on the model is as follows:

- Hypothesis 1: Green product has a positive effect on green trust.
- Hypothesis 2: Green advertising has a positive effect on green trust
- Hypothesis 3: Green trust has a positive effect on purchase decisions
- Hypothesis 4: Green Trust mediates the relationship between green products and purchase decisions
- Hypothesis 5: Green Trust mediates the relationship between green advertising and purchase decisions
- Hypothesis 6: Green Product has a positive effect on Purchase Decision
- Hypothesis 7: Green Advertising has a positive effect on Purchase Decision

III. RESEARCH METHODS

In this research, it is quantitative in nature and the method to be used is descriptive with a verification approach. The hypothesis testing will be carried out by means of the verification method. In addition to explaining the relationship between the variables to be studied, it will also be sought to what extent the relationship between variables partially or simultaneously in the study, namely Green Product and Green Advertising are the independent variables, purchase decision is the dependent variable and green trust is the intervening variable. Based on the formula from Hair et al., (2014), the number of samples to be used in the study is 110 samples. The hypothesis testing will be carried out using the Partial Least Square (PLS) based Structural Equation Model (SEM) method. In this study,

there is a complex model and also a limited number of samples, therefore in data analysis SmartPLS software will be used which uses a random multiplication method. Therefore the assumption of normality will not be a problem. SmartPLS also does not require a minimum sample, so it is suitable for this study. PLS-SEM analysis will be carried out with 2 sub-models, the outer model and the inner model.

IV. RESEARCH RESULT

A. Characteristics of Respondents

Based on the research conducted, the number of respondents who filled out the questionnaire was 156 people. So after conducting the questionnaire, it can be seen the characteristics of the respondents based on age, occupation, education and gender of the respondents. Of the 156 respondents, the female sex dominated as many as 102 respondents or 65.6%. Most of the respondents were aged 17-30 years, amounting to 70 respondents or 44.6%. S1 education dominated the respondents as many as 94 people or 59.9%. And based on the questionnaires distributed, it can be seen that as many as 73 respondents or 46.5% of respondents have other jobs.

B. Validity Test Results

If the value of outer loading ≥ 0.7 then it will be said to be valid. However, after the development of new models and indicators, the value of outer loading between 0.5 - 0.6 can still be said to be valid (Yamin and Kurniawan, 2011 in Haryono, 2017: 405). From the table below it can be seen that all values from outer loading have values above 0.7 so that they are declared valid.

Variabel	Item	Outer Loading	Batasan Outer Loading	Keputusan
Green Product (X1)	1	0.801	0.7	Valid
	2	0.858	0.7	Valid
	3	0.908	0.7	Valid
	4	0.729	0.7	Valid
Green Advertising (X2)	1	0.823	0.7	Valid
	2	0.880	0.7	Valid
	3	0.908	0.7	Valid
Green Trust (Z)	1	0.846	0.7	Valid
	2	0.870	0.7	Valid
	3	0.758	0.7	Valid
	4	0.715	0.7	Valid
Purchase Decision (Y)	1	0.828	0.7	Valid
	2	0.838	0.7	Valid
	3	0.772	0.7	Valid
	4	0.813	0.7	Valid

Table 2: Validity Test Results

➤ *AVE Test Result*

The ideal value of AVE is 0.5 which means that the convergent validity value is good, so it can be interpreted that latent variables can explain more than half of the

variance of the indicators. The results of the test on the AVE value can be found in the table below. Based on the table, all variables have an AVE value above 0.5 so that it can be said that these variables have good validity.

Variabel	AVE	AVE Limit	Decision
Green Product (X1)	0.685	0.500	Valid
Green Advertising (X2)	0.759	0.500	Valid
Green Trust (Z)	0.640	0.500	Valid
Purchase Decision (Y)	0.661	0.500	Valid

Table 3: AVE Test Result

C. Reliability Test Results

Based on Chin (1998), the condition used to assess reliability is the value of Chronbach's Alpha. Composite Reliability must have a value greater than 0.70 for confirmatory research. Whereas for exploratory research the

value of 0.60 - 0.70 is still acceptable. Based on the table below, it shows that Croanbach alpha and composite reliability are greater than 0.7. So it can be seen that the consistency and stability in this study is high.

Variabel	Croanbach Alpha	Composite Reability	Reability Limit	Decision
Green Product (X1)	0.846	0.896	0.700	Valid
Green Advertising (X2)	0.841	0.904	0.700	Valid
Green Trust (Z)	0.811	0.876	0.700	Valid
Purchase Decision (Y)	0.829	0.886	0.700	Valid

Table 4: Reliability Test Results

➤ Discriminant Validity Result

If the value of the AVE square root in each construct has a greater value than the correlation value between the constructs, it can be seen that the variable has good discriminant validity. Based on the table below it can be

seen that all the indicators have a greater correlation coefficient value on the variables compared to the other variables, so that it can be seen that each indicator in the block is a variable constituent.

	Green Product (X1)	Green Advertising (X2)	Green Trust (Z)	Purchase Decision (Y)
X1.1	0.801	0.449	0.549	0.489
X1.2	0.858	0.474	0.477	0.314
X1.3	0.908	0.481	0.514	0.356
X1.4	0.729	0.407	0.354	0.287
X2.1	0.520	0.823	0.537	0.308
X2.2	0.453	0.880	0.577	0.403
X2.3	0.468	0.909	0.649	0.419
Y1	0.408	0.385	0.493	0.828
Y2	0.376	0.322	0.527	0.838
Y3	0.312	0.320	0.519	0.772
Y4	0.345	0.389	0.512	0.813
Z1	0.458	0.488	0.846	0.621
Z2	0.542	0.585	0.870	0.590
Z3	0.522	0.524	0.758	0.372
Z4	0.319	0.469	0.716	0.409

Table 5: Cross Loading Result

Furthermore, discriminant validity will be measured by comparing the AVE root value of each variable. Based on the table below, it can be seen that the value of the root

AVE of each variable is higher than the value of the correlation between variables in the model. So that it can be stated to have good discriminant validity.

	Green Product (X1)	Green Advertising (X2)	Green Trust (Z)	Purchase Decision (Y)
Green Product (X1)	0.871			
Green Advertising (X2)	0.548	0.827		
Green Trust (Z)	0.677	0.585	0.800	
Purchase Decision (Y)	0.436	0.451	0.631	0.813

Table 6: AVE Root Value Results and Correlation Between Constructs

➤ Analyse R Square

	R Square
Green Trust (Z)	0.524
Purchase Decision (Y)	0.409

Table 7: Result R Square

Based on Table 7, the R square value of green trust has a high influence, while the r square value of the purchase decision has a moderate effect.

➤ *F Square analysis*

If the value of F2 is 0.02 it can be said that the exogenous latent effect is small, if 0.15 it can be said to be a medium exogenous latent effect, and if the value is 0.35 it can be said to have a large exogenous latent effect (Ghozali and Latan, 2015: 81). In Table 8 it can be seen that the value

of Green Product on Green Trust has a value of 0.138, so it includes a moderate effect. Green Advertising on Green Trust has a value of 0.302, so it includes high influence. Green Trust on Purchase Decision has a value of 0.663, so it includes high influence. Green Product on Purchase Decision has a value of 0.017, so it includes a low influence. Green Advertising on Purchase Decision has a value of 0.000, so it includes a low influence.

	<i>Green Product (X1)</i>	<i>Green Advertising (X2)</i>	<i>Green Trust (Z)</i>	<i>Purchase Decision (Y)</i>
<i>Green Product (X1)</i>			0.302	0.000
<i>Green Advertising (X2)</i>			0.138	0.017
<i>Green Trust (Z)</i>				0.663
<i>Purchase Decision (Y)</i>				

Table 8: Result F Square

➤ *Predictive Relevance (Q²)*

If $Q^2 > 0$ it can be said that the model has predictive relevance while the value of $Q^2 < 0$ can be said the model lacks predictive relevance (Ghozali and Latan, 2015: 81).

Based on the table below, it can be seen that the Q2 values are 0.317 and 0.255 so that it can be said that the model has predictive relevance.

	<i>SSO</i>	<i>SSE</i>	<i>Q²(=1-SSE/SSO)</i>
<i>Green Product (X1)</i>	330.000	330.000	0
<i>Green Advertising (X2)</i>	440.000	440.000	0
<i>Green Trust (Z)</i>	440.000	300.574	0.317
<i>Purchase Decision (Y)</i>	440.000	327.936	0.255

Table 9: Results of Q2 Value on SmartPLS

➤ *Model Fit Test*

	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.080
d_ ULS	0.774
d_ G	0.412
Chi-Square	250.905
NFI	0.749

Table 10: Model Fit Test Results

Based on Table 10, it can be seen that the model has an SRMR value of 0.080 so that it can be said that the model meets the goodness of fit model criteria.

D. Results of the Direct Effect Hypothesis Test

	Hypothesis	Coefficient Std Value	T Statistic	P-value	Keterangan
H1	Green Product → Green Trust	0,306	4,323	0,000	Terdukung
H2	Green Advertising → Green Trust	0,509	6,973	0,000	Terdukung
H3	Green Trust → <i>Purchase Decision</i>	0,569	4,425	0,000	Terdukung
H4	Green Product → <i>Purchase Decision</i>	0,129	1,217	0,224	Tidak Terdukung
H5	Green Advertising → <i>Purchase Decision</i>	0,020	0,158	0,875	Tidak Terdukung

Table 11: Results of the Direct Effect Hypothesis Test

Based on Table 11, it can be seen that the green product variable has a significant positive effect on the green trust variable, the green advertising variable has a significant positive effect on the green trust variable, the green trust variable has a significant positive effect on the purchase decision variable, the green product variable has no effect on purchasing decisions and Green advertising has no effect on purchasing decisions.

➤ *Test the Effect of Mediation Variables*

The test results for the effect of the mediating variable can be seen in Table 12, if the P value is below 0.05, it can be said that the independent variable has an effect on the dependent variable through the mediating variable. The following are the results of the mediation variable influence test:

	Original Sample	Sample Mean	STDEV	T Statistics	P Values
Green Advertising -> Green Trust -> Purchase Decision	0.290	0.283	0.077	3.757	0.000
Green Product -> Green Trust -> Purchase Decision	0.174	0.177	0.057	3.049	0.002

Table 12: Indirect Effect Test Results

	Original Sample	Sample Mean	STDEV	T Statistics	P Values
Green Advertising (X2) -> Green Trust (Z)	0.509	0.506	0.073	6.973	0.000
Green Advertising (X2) -> Purchase Decision (Y)	0.207	0.274	0.108	2.505	0.013
Green Product (X1) -> Green Trust (Z)	0.306	0.317	0.071	4.323	0.000
Green Product (X1) -> Purchase Decision (Y)	0.303	0.317	0.096	3.152	0.002
Green Trust (Z) -> Purchase Decision (Y)	0.569	0.559	0.129	4.425	0.000

Table 13: Total Effects Test

Based on Tables 12 and 13, the following conclusions are drawn:

Hipotesis		Nilai Std Koefisien	T Statistic	P-value	Kesimpulan
H6	Green Product → Green Trust → Purchase Decision	0,174	3,049	0,002	Memediasi
H7	Green Product → Green Trust → Purchase Decision	0,290	3,757	0,000	Memediasi

Table 14: Results of the Indirect Effect Hypothesis Test

It can be seen from Table 14 that it can be concluded that the Green Trust variable can mediate the relationship between the green product variable and also the purchase decision. To determine the effect of partial mediation or full mediation, it can be seen in the Total Effect output. From the Total Effect output, it is known that the influence of the green trust variable (X1) on the purchase decision variable (Y) is significant. So that there is the effect of quasi-mediation/quasi mediating/partial mediating. The Green Trust variable can also mediate the relationship between green advertising variables and purchase decisions. To determine the effect of partial mediation or full mediation, it can be seen in the Total Effect output. From the Total Effect output, it is known that the effect of Green trust (X1) on purchase decision (Y) is significant. resulting in the effect of pseudo-mediating/quasi-mediating/partial mediating.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This study aims to determine the effect of variables such as green trust, green product, green advertising and purchase decision, the results of the research conducted, it can be concluded that the green product variable has a significant positive effect on the green trust variable, the green advertising variable has a significant positive effect on the variable green trust. The green trust variable has a significant positive effect on the purchase decision variable. The green product variable has no effect on the purchase decision variable. The green advertising variable has no effect on the purchase decision variable. The green trust variable can mediate the relationship between the green product variable and the purchase decision variable. The green trust variable can mediate the relationship between green advertising variables and purchase decision variables. Based on the research, there are several deficiencies so that later it is necessary to do a review by expanding the variables used and deepening the research indicators related to green products and expanding theoretical studies regarding different research objects.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Albari dan Indah, S. 2018. The Influence of Product Price on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions. *Journal Integrative Business and Economics Research*. 7 (2) : 328 – 337
- [2.] Albino, V., Balice, A., dan Dangelico, R. M. 2009. Environmental Strategies and Green Product Development: An Overview on Sustainability-Driven Companies. *Business Strategy and the Environment*. 18 (2) : 83-96
- [3.] Alshura, M. S dan Abdelrahim, M. Z. 2016. Impact of Brand Trust, Green Brand Awareness, Green Brand Image, and Green Perceived Value on Consumer's Intension to Use Green Products: An Empirical Study of Jordanian Consumers. *International Journal of Advanced Research*. 4 (2) : 1423-1433
- [4.] Anjani, N dan Ni, M. A. A. 2016. Pengaruh *Green Advertising, Eco Brand* dan *Green Trust* terhadap Perilaku Pembelian Produk Hijau di Kota Denpasar. *E-Jurnal Manajemen Unud*. 5 (5) : 2814-2841
- [5.] Anvar, M dan Marike, V. 2014. Attitudes and Purchase Behaviour of Green Products among Generation Y Consumers in South Africa. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*. 5 (21) : 183-194
- [6.] Ardiansyah, L., Zainul, A., dan Dahlan, F. 2015. Pengaruh Daya Tarik Iklan Terhadap Efektivitas Iklan. *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis*. 23 (2) : 75-84
- [7.] Astini, R. 2016. Implikasi Green Brand, Green Satisfaction dan Green Trust Terhadap Loyalitas Pelanggan (Studi Kasus Pada Konsumen AMDK Galon Merk AQUA di Wilayah Serpong Utara). *Jurnal Manajemen*. 20 (1) : 19-34
- [8.] Berchicci, L. dan Bodewes, W. 2005. Bridging Environmental Issues with New Product Development. *Business Strategy and the Environment*. 14 (5) : 272-285

- [9.] Brata, B. H., Shilvana, H., dan Hapzi, A. 2017. The Influence of Quality Products, Price, Promotion, and Location to Product Purchase Decision on Nitchi At PT. Jaya Swarasa Agung in Central Jakarta. *Saudi Journal of Business and Management Studies*. 1 (2) : 433-445
- [10.] Cahyani, N. L. T. H. dan I Made, W. 2017. Peran Green Trust dalam Memediasi Pengaruh Green Product Perception terhadap Green Repurchase Intention. *E-Jurnal Manajemen Unud*. 6 (6) : 2933-2966
- [11.] Cannon, J. P., William, D. P., dan Jerome, M. Basic Marketing: A Global-Managerial Approach. McGraw-Hill. New York
- [12.] Chen, T. B. dan Chai, L. T. 2010. Attitude towards Environment and Green Products: Consumers Perspective. *Management Science and Engineering*. 4 (2) : 27-39
- [13.] Coleman, L. J., Bahnan, N., Kelkar, M., dan Curry, N. (2011). Walking The Walk: How the Theory of Reasoned Action Explains Adult and Student Intentions to Go Green. *Journal of Applied Business Research*. 27 (3) : 107-116
- [14.] Delafrooz, N., Mohammad, T., dan Bahareh, N. 2014. Effect of Green Marketing on Consumer Purchase Behavior. *QScience Connect*. 5 : 1-9
- [15.] Dewanti, T. R., Suharyono, dan Aniesa, S. B. 2018. Pengaruh Green Brand Image Terhadap Green Trust Serta Implikasinya Terhadap Green Purchase Intention. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*. 62 (1) : 99-107
- [16.] Durif, F., Caroline, B., dan Charles, J. 2010. In Search of a Green Product Definition. *Innovative Marketing*. 6 (1) : 25-33
- [17.] D'Souza, C dan Taghian, M. 2005. Green Advertising Effects on Attitude and Choice of Advertising Themes. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*. 17 (3) : 51-66
- [18.] Firmansyah, M. A. 2018. Perilaku Konsumen (Sikap dan Pemasaran). Deepublish. Yogyakarta
- [19.] Ghozali dan Latan, 2015, "Partial Least Squares, Konsep Teknik dan Aplikasi Menggunakan Program SmartPLS 3.0". Edisi 2. Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro, Semarang. Hal: 77, 81, 78, 83
- [20.] Gokirmakli, C., Mustafa, B., dan Eugenia, T. 2017. Behaviours of Consumers on EU Eco-Label: A Case Study for Romanian Consumers. *Bulgarian Journal of Agricultural Science*. 23 (3) : 512-517
- [21.] Halim, J dan Sesilya, K. 2016. Pengaruh Green Perceived Value, Green Perceived Risk, Green Trust, dan Perceived Value Terhadap Green Purchase Intention Produk AC Low Watt di Surabaya. *Agora*. 4 (1) : 404-413
- [22.] Haryono, Siswoyo, 2017, "Metode SEM Untuk Penelitian Manajemen dengan AMOS Lisrel PLS". Cetakan I. Penerbit Luxima Metro Media, Jakarta. Hal: 405, 375, 421, 410, 255
- [23.] Hassan, R. 2016. Customer Perception of Green Advertising in The Context of Eco-Friendly FMCGs. *Contemporary Management Research*. 12 (2) : 169-182
- [24.] Hasanuddin, Joseph, K., Putu, I. M., Nastiti, T. W., dan Bernardus, S. 2011. Anxieties/Desires: 90 Insights for Marketing to Youth, Women, Netizen. PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama. Jakarta
- [25.] Hermawan dan Hasibuan, 2016, "Analisis Pengaruh Tingkat Pengalaman Dan Coaching Style Terhadap Kualitas Kepemimpinan Manajer Proyek Dalam Upaya Peningkatan Produktivitas di PT.J". *Jurnal PASTI Volume XI No. 1*, 84 - 97, Universitas Mercu Buana, Jln. Meruya Selatan No. 1 Jakarta. Hal:88.
- [26.] Hussein, Ananda, 2015, "Penelitian Bisnis dan Manajemen Menggunakan Partial Least Squares (PLS) dengan SmartPLS 3.0". Modul Ajar, Jurusan Manajemen, Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Brawijaya. Hal: 25
- [27.] IHEMEZIE, E. J., IKENNA, C. U., dan AMAKA, P. N. 2017. Impact of 'Green' Product Label Standards on Consumer Behaviour: A Systematic Review Analysis. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*. 8 (9) : 666-684
- [28.] Jambeck, J. R., Roland, G., Chris, W., Theodore, R. S., Miriam P., Anthony, A., Ramani, N., dan Kara, L. L. 2015. Plastic Waste Inputs from Land Into the Ocean. *Science*. 347 (6223) : 768-771
- [29.] Jorgensen, R. B. dan Oystein, M. 2015. Eco Labelling from the Consumer Perspective: A Case Study of Indoor Paint Products. *Research for Consumer*. 27 (1) : 1-25
- [30.] Kaihatu, T. S. 2014. Manajemen Pengemasan. Andi. Yogyakarta Kong, W., Amran, H., Rini, S. S., dan Jaratin, L. 2014. The Influence of Consumers Perception of Green Products on Green Purchase Intention. *International Journal of Asian Science*. 4 (8) : 924-939
- [31.] Khoiruman, M dan Aris, T. H. 2017. Green Purchasing Behavior Analysis of Government Policy About Paid Plastic Bags. *Indonesian Journal of Sustainability Accounting and Management*. 1 (1) : 31-39
- [32.] Khuong, M. N dan Hoang, T. M. D. 2016. Personal Factors Affecting Consumer Purchase Decision towards Men Skin Care Products. *International Journal of Trade Economics and Finance*. 7 (2) : 44-50
- [33.] Kurniawan, S. 2014. The Influence of Green Marketingon Green Satisfaction Mediated by Perceived Quality and Its Impact to Green Trust in Injection Motorcycle. *Journal The Winners*. 15 (2) : 85-94
- [34.] Ling, K. C., Dazmin, B. D., Tan, H. P., Kay H. K., dan Padzil, H. 2011. Perceive Risk, Perceived Technology, Online Trust for the Online Purchase Intention in Malaysia. *International Journal of Business and Management*. 6 (6): 167-182
- [35.] Nugroho, E. 2018. Prinsip-prinsip Menyusun Kuesioner. UB Press. Malang
- [36.] Nurmahdi, Adi, 2021. *The effect of Price and Brand Image on Purchase Decisions and their Implications on Consumer Satisfaction of Ebara Pump Products in Jabodetabek*

- [37.] Nursanti, T. D. dan Melisa. 2011. Analisis Pengaruh *Green Product* dan *Green Advertising* terhadap Keterlibatan Konsumen dan Dampaknya pada purchase decision Konsumen Laksmie Florist. *Binus Business Review*. 2 (2): 1077-1093
- [38.] Permana, Dudi, 2020, *The implication of green marketing that influence the customer awareness towards their purchase decision*
- [39.] Priyatno, Duwi, 2013, “*Mandiri Belajar Analisis Data Dengan SPSS*”, Yogyakarta: Media Kom.
- [40.] Rasaputra, C. J. dan Sam, C. Y. 2015. An Investigation on Consumer Purchasing Decision of Green Products: The Case of Singapore. *International Journal of Advances in Management and Economics*. 4 (2) : 87-94
- [41.] Richards, L. 2013. Examining Green Advertising and Its Impact on Consumer Skepticism and Purchasing Patterns. *The Elon Journal of Undergraduate Research in Communications*. 4 (2) : 78-90
- [42.] Ridwan, M., Achmad, F. D. H., dan Aniesa, S. B. 2018. Pengaruh Green Product, Green Advertising, dan Green Brand Terhadap purchase decision. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*. 55 (1) : 80-90
- [43.] Ruangguttamanun, C. 2014. The Use of Appeals in Green Printed Advertisements: A Case of Product Orientation and Organizational Image Orientation Ads. *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*. 8 (9) : 2988- 2993
- [44.] Saabar, S. S., Abuzar, A. H., Antashah, M. N., dan Khairudin, M. 2012. Measuring Trust on Green Advertising Claims: An Exploratory Study on Higher Institution Student towards Malaysian Green Advertisements. *IPEDR*. 56 (5) : 22-27
- [45.] Sdrolia, E dan Grigoris, Z. 2019. A Comprehensive Review for Green Product Term: From Definition to Evaluation. *Economic Surveys*. 33 (1) : 150-178
- [46.] Salwa, M., Mustapha, K., dan Amina, A. 2017. Green Advertising and Environmentally Consumption: The Level of Awareness and Moroccan Costumer’s Perception. *Journal of Business and Management*. 19 (8) : 1 – 11
- [47.] Sanidewi, H. dan Eristia, L. P. 2018. The Role of Perceived Green Marketing and Brand Equity on Green Purchasing Decision. *Diponegoro International Journal of Business*. 1 (2) : 14-25
- [48.] Santoso, I dan Rengganis, F. 2016. Green Packaging, Green Product, Green Advertising, Persepsi, dan Minat Beli Konsumen. *Jurnal Ilmiah Kel. Dan Kons*. 9 (2) : 147-158
- [49.] Saragih, C. V. B. 2013. Pengaruh Kualitas Produk, Ketersediaan Produk, dan Gaya Hidup terhadap purchase decision Produk Lulur Mandi Source Ayu di Jakarta. *MIX*. 3 (2) : 231-246
- [50.] Shidiq, A. M. N. dan Arry, W. 2018. Minat Pembelian Produk Ramah Lingkungan: Dampak Pengetahuan dan Sikap Berwawasan Lingkungan. *Sekretaris dan Administrasi Bisnis*. 2 (2) : 60-73
- [51.] Sofyani, Hafiez, 2013, *Modul Praktik Partial Least Square (PLS)*, Universitas Muhammadiyah, Yogyakarta. Hal: 27, 28, 34
- [52.] Song, S. Y. dan Youn K. K. 2018. A Human-Centered Approach to Green Apparel Advertising: Decision Tree Predictive Modeling of Consumer Choice. *Sustainability*. 10 (3688) : 1-20
- [53.] Syafrina, I. 2016. Pengaruh *Green Product* (Tissue Tessa) Terhadap purchase decision. *e-Proceeding of Applied Science*. 2 (2) : 430-434
- [54.] Tiwari, S. 2011. Green Marketing–Emerging Dimensions. *Journal of Business Excellence*. 2 (1) : 18-23
- [55.] Trott, S. dan Vinod, V. S. 2016. Brand Equity: An Indian Perspective. PHI Learning Private Limited. New Delhi
- [56.] Widarjono, Agus, 2015, “*Analisis Multivariate Terapan Dengan Program SPSS, AMOS, dan SmartPLS*”. Edisi II, UPP STIM YKPN, Yogyakarta